

**Aitana: Promoting Circular Economy Through Electronic Waste Management in
Kenya**

BSc. (Hons) in Software Engineering

Mohamed Ahmed Yasin

Supervisor

David Neza Tuyishimire

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Dedication

I dedicate this degree and dissertation project to my loving parents, **Ahmed Yasin Elmi** and **Saynab Hassan Ibrahim**.

My father, who passed away 14 years ago (May Allah have mercy on him) was the first person who believed in me and taught me the value of education. He always inspired me to push the boundaries and expand my horizons. Although he is no longer with us, his wisdom and the lessons he taught me still guide me every single day.

My mother has been my best friend and biggest supporter. Her beautiful prayers, infinite love and empowering words have helped me navigate through every challenge in life. Her hardwork, kindness and bubbly personality always remind me to dream big.

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Finally, I would like to thank **the Mastercard Foundation** for funding my education and giving me the opportunity to continue my higher education studies.

Declaration

I, Mohamed Ahmed Yasin, hereby declare that this capstone project named “Aitana: upcycling electronic-waste in Eastleigh, Nairobi” is completely my own original work and has not been submitted or written by any other person or organization.

I also declare that all sources of information I used while writing this project are properly acknowledged through citations and references.

This capstone project is a partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of my Bachelor of Science (Honours) in Software Engineering at the African Leadership University (ALU) in Rwanda.

Student Signature: *Mohamedyasin*

Name: [Mohamed Ahmed Yasin]

Date: 31-07-2025

Supervisor Signature: *David Neza Tuyishimire*

Name: [David Neza Tuyishimire]

Date: 03-08-2025

Abstract

Electronic waste (e-waste) is a fastly growing environmental challenge in many countries around the world, with over 53.6 million tonnes generated globally in 2019, expected to reach 74.7 million tonnes by 2030 (Forti et al., 2020). In Kenya, the number of e-waste generated annually rose from just 3,000 in 2012 to 51,000 tonnes in 2021 (The Regional E-waste Management Steering Committee, 2022). Nairobi's e-waste management relies on manual collection and disposal, with limited focus on reuse or e-waste upcycling. The Eastleigh neighborhood, which is a major business hub, faces a significant challenge of e-waste which contributes to local waste problems.

Although some organizations like the WEEE Centre, have made tangible contributions to Kenya's e-waste management and recycling efforts, there still remains a wide gap in software-based solutions that encourage creative reuse of e-waste and raise educational awareness about its hazards on the environment and the people's health.

This capstone project proposes Aitana, a smart mobile application designed to classify eight common e-waste categories such as mobile phones and laptops through Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) with an accuracy rate of 80%. The classification system generates one fun fact and two practical reuse ideas per e-waste item. Aitana also offers educational resources and a chatbot restricted for e-waste, circular economy and sustainability topics.

At the end, Aitana was tested with 10-15 residents of Eastleigh and their feedback indicated that over 60% promised to repurpose their e-waste materials after interacting with the mobile application. The results also showed that harnessing artificial intelligence with sustainability education can reduce improper e-waste disposal, promote the circular economy and raise awareness in urban communities like Eastleigh.

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List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

AI : Artificial Intelligence

CNN : Convolutional Neural Network

E-WASTE : Electronic waste

ERD : Entity-Relationship Diagram

EWIK : E-Waste Initiative Kenya

ML : Machine Learning

UML : Unified Modeling Language

WEEE : Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment

YOLO : You Only Look Once

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction and Background

Electronic waste (e-waste) is among the fastest growing waste issues in the world and it needs urgent solutions. According to the World Bank (2021), the number of global waste is expected to grow and reach 3.4 billion tonnes by 2050. In Kenya, the annual electronic waste generation increased from 3,000 metric tonnes in 2012 to 51,000 metric tonnes in 2021. Nairobi, the capital city of Kenya produces over 2,400 tonnes of waste every day, with a notable proportion made up of discarded electronics (Environmental Best Practices in Waste Management, 2022).

Eastleigh, one of Nairobi's bustling business neighborhoods, is particularly affected by e-waste due to its dense population and thriving electronics market. Many electronic items like computers, televisions and phones are commonly traded, used and disposed improperly. A high number of these items contain reusable components so they need to be creatively redesigned into useful items.

Waste management in Kenya heavily relies on human labor to collect and handle e-waste. Companies in this sector recycle or resell e-waste to other companies that are interested in recycling or refurbishing the discarded items. Some of the primary organizations in Kenya's e-waste management are WEEE Centre and E-waste Initiative Kenya (EWIK). Both of these organizations mainly focus on e-waste recycling and disposal rather than having software systems that identify e-waste and encourage refurbishing and reusing.

This project will introduce a software application that leverages machine learning to classify common e-waste objects and recommends practical reuse ideas to users. It also promotes circular economy practice and sustainability by educating and encouraging users to not dispose of e-waste and to turn it into useful items.

1.2 Problem statement

At present, nearly 80 percent of the global e-waste is not recycled properly, handled badly and often ends in landfills. (Ghimire & Ariya, 2020). In Kenya's capital, Nairobi, managing electronic waste is a challenge and most organizations mostly focus on collecting old electronic items and recycling or dumping them away into the environment. Studies show that in Eastleigh, one of Nairobi's business neighborhoods, large amounts of electronic waste are generated every day as thousands of people purchase, use and throw away items like mobile phones and computers (Hansen et al., 2022).

Many of the discarded electronic waste items still have reusable components that could be turned into useful items. However, due to limited resources and awareness, these opportunities are missed.

The top two closest existing solutions of this project in Kenya are the EWIK and WEEE Centre.

- EWIK is an organization that offers awareness and training programs about e-waste recycling in Nairobi (Maina, 2025). EWIK does not offer any software solutions that help people scan their electronics and offers reusable ideas.
- WEEE Centre is a big e-waste recycling and disposal company that works on e-waste collecting, dismantling and disposing (Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre - KKCF, 2023). They primarily focus on safe e-waste disposal and recycling and do not offer any software solutions for e-waste management.

Therefore, there is a big need for a solution that can address this challenge. This research introduces Aitana, a software solution that utilizes Machine Learning to help users identify e-waste items and learn new ways to reuse them. Aitana is also providing educational and awareness tools to users.

1.3 Project's main objective

The main objective of this study is to develop a software-based solution that tackles the increasing e-waste disposal in Eastleigh while giving users relevant ideas of how they can reuse the e-waste items, thereby encouraging circular economy and sustainable innovation.

1.3.1 List of the specific objectives

The top three specific objectives of this project are:

- Reducing the number of electronic waste items in the Eastleigh neighborhood by at least 30% through increased reuse and educational awareness campaigns.
- Developing and designing an image classification model that detects the uploaded e-waste images with at least 80% accuracy rate.
- Promoting sustainability and circular economy within the Eastleigh community by encouraging at least 60% of the users to reuse their e-waste items instead of throwing it away.

1.4 Research questions

1. What are the key challenges and barriers to effective e-waste management in Kenya?
2. What are the most common e-waste items discarded in Eastleigh, Nairobi?
3. What is the level of awareness and education among the Kenyan population regarding the importance of responsible e-waste disposal and recycling?
4. What types of reuse are most suitable for the identified e-waste objects?
5. How helpful and easy will users find the software solution when it comes to e-waste?

1.5 Project scope

This project will mainly be tested in the Eastleigh neighbourhood in Nairobi, Kenya. Eastleigh is known for its business, dense population, and lots of urban waste. At first, the plan is to test it with 10-15 residents to assess the software's functionality and practicality. The research does not focus on recycling or refurbishment of e-waste materials. Its primary

goal is to identify e-waste items, suggest reuse ideas with tutorials and educate communities about how dumping e-waste harms people's health and the environment.

1.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethics are a crucial part of the research and it must be carefully considered to protect users and encourage fairness.

First, privacy and consent are included in the software system. In the Mobile application, users are asked their permission to upload their images to the system so they receive the reuse suggestions available. Their data will be protected, stored and managed in compliance with Kenya's Data Protection Act (2020).

Second, to manage and avoid potential bias in the machine learning model, the dataset that will be trained includes diverse images of e-waste items. To do this, the project will follow bias detection techniques recommended by IBM's AI Fairness 360 toolkit (Bellamy et al., 2019).

Third, the solution will prevent to recommend inappropriate or unsafe reuse ideas. This safety and wellness of the users will always be a priority. For vulnerable users, such as people with limited literacy skills, the software solution will use simple language and emojis that they can easily understand when they see.

1.7 Significance and Justification

The success of this project will contribute to the reduction of e-waste items discarded in the open spaces or landfills in the Eastleigh neighborhood, Nairobi. Instead of disposing of old or non-functional e-waste items, users will be able to repurpose their e-waste items into useful items.

This project will support Kenya's circular economy goals which encourages the transition to a sustainable economy model that boosts efficiency in resources and cutting down wastes

(Muriithi & Innocent Ngare, 2023). The innovation and creativity of this project also empowers the Eastleigh community to actively manage their e-waste properly and participate in the waste management efforts the government of Kenya is doing.

1.8 Research Budget

Item	Cost (RWF)
Model Training (Google Colab)	15000
Deployment Plans	12000
Gemini API	10000
Transport and Survey Collection	10000
Total	47000

Table 1: Research Budget

1.9 Research Timeline

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

At present, e-waste is one of the biggest and fastest growing environmental challenges happening worldwide, posing risks to our health and ecosystem. In places like Nairobi, particularly in the Eastleigh neighborhood, massive volumes of e-waste are discarded every day, where many of them contain both toxic dangerous materials and reusable parts (Muiruri et al., 2020). Most of the existing solutions focus on recycling and disposal and neglect opportunities for keeping and reusing e-waste items. Addressing this important gap is vital for encouraging sustainability and reducing health and environmental harm.

The recent advances in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning have enhanced the identification and classification of e-waste items with high accuracy, although they mostly stop at detecting items. They do not encourage the reuse of e-waste materials, suggest creative reuse ideas for reuse, or educate users about the health and environmental hazards of inappropriate e-waste disposal.

This chapter concentrates on finding software-centric studies about AI-driven e-waste classification and management systems. The methodology used to review the literature is systematic search of journals, research papers, conference proceedings and other online resources such as ScienceDirect, IEEE Xplore, Google Scholar and Github repositories. The literature review used in this chapter found more than 10 relevant publications from the last five years.

2.2 Historical Background of the Research Topic

In the last two decades, e-waste has been one of the fastest growing pollution issues in the world (Kiddee et al., 2013). According to (Forti et al., 2020), more than 53.6 million metric tons of e-waste were released around the world in 2019 and unfortunately, the number is

projected to grow to 74.7 million metric tons by 2030. Most of the -waste generated is improperly managed, particularly in developing countries where weak governance and lack of awareness are challenges. This poor e-waste management can cause both health risks and environmental pollution.

The latest developments in Artificial intelligence and Machine Learning are offering possibilities for controlling e-waste more responsibly and effectively. For example, a recent project by Sivakumar et al., (2025) built and developed an AI-based deep learning model that can classify various types of waste from images with high accuracy. The model performs well on large scale datasets and leverages EfficientNet and DenseNet architectures. This shows that AI can be used to address waste classification and improve and expedite the process of recycling (El jaouhari et al., 2024).

Nevertheless, most AI system solutions now focus only on classification and recycling, not on educating people about e-waste disasters and suggesting practical and alternative ways to reuse discarded e-waste items. This is the gap that Aitana aims to address. Aitana is promoting Kenya's circular economy's goals, which is to minimize waste and promote their reuse as long as possible. According to Muriithi & Ngare (2023), Kenya adopted the circular economy system in 2021, and since then, the country has been working on reducing pollution and enhancing sustainability.

2.3 Overview of Existing System

Electronic waste (e-waste) has been a big challenge for the last two decades, where the usage of electronics grew tremendously (Waema & Mureithi, 2008). Globally, several software-based solutions are developed to address the e-waste issues and here are some of them:

- **Recycleye:** this is a UK based start-up that developed a computer vision system and robotics system that can detect and classify waste items (Recycleye | EIT, 2019).
- **EcoSort:** this is a machine learning based project that was designed to classify different types of waste items. The aim of this project is to reduce landfill waste and support environmental conservation (Kalaria & Student, 2023).
- **TrashOut:** this is a mobile application that was built to report illegal dumping sites and encourage environmental cleanliness (TrashOut: Locate and Get Rid of Illegal Dumps, 2011).

2.4 Review of Related Work

E-waste is a global issue that is causing environmental problems for the last decades and there are lots of people who are gaining awareness and trying to solve this challenge. In recent years, many researchers have explored how Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence can help tackle e-waste management challenges.

A study by (Mustapha et al., 2025) introduced a hybrid deep learning model that combines Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for classification with YOLOv8 for object detection. The model leverages YOLOv8 to locate waste items and then applies CNN to classify them into compost or non-compost. The model was trained on a specialized dataset and it achieves a high overall accuracy of 0.88 and high performance F1 score of 0.86. The study highlights the effectiveness and efficiency of combining detection and classification techniques to tackle real world waste identification efforts.

Another study by (Zhou, 2022) developed a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) that automates the classification of e-waste into four types. This model was created to separate and sort e-waste items who need urgent attention. The model has achieved a training

accuracy of 96.9% and a validation accuracy of 93.9%, which shows that the model performed well. This study highlighted the potential of machine learning to decrease lower demands and speed up the e-waste recycling processes.

(Handhayani & Hendryli, 2022) developed Leboh, an Android-based mobile application that uses the EfficientNet-Lite model from TensorFlow Lite to classify different types of waste. The model was validated and trained on a dataset containing 15,190 images across 11 categories of waste including plastic, metal, paper, glass, textiles. It achieved a testing accuracy of 95.39%, showing high effectiveness and functionality. During the user testing period, the application reached an accuracy of 82.5%, with plastic waste being the most regularly detected waste category.

Roboflow is another company that introduced a web platform for e-waste classification and allows users to upload images (East West University, 2023). The Roboflow platform either enables users to train their own models or leverage pre-trained computer vision models like YOLO.

Overall, while these above work and contributions highlight the research and potential of AI in electronic waste management, they mostly focus on just detection or recycling. The main gap that Aitana will fill in and focus on is to educate people about e-waste health and environment risks and develop a machine learning classification that users upload e-waste images and then give them easy and practical reusable ideas.

2.5 Strengths and Weakness of the Existing System(s)

Each of the existing systems and solutions that address e-waste challenges have their own strengths and weaknesses (Ghulam & Abushammala, 2023). Many of these organizations also offer good services to tackle e-waste challenges.. For example, companies like

EWIK, WEEE Centre, Recycleye and TrashOut use cutting edge technology and help with making awareness and recycling efforts but they do not offer e-waste image classification software-based systems and applications.

This project will fill that gap by introducing a smart software application that not only classifies e-waste items through image classification but also tells the importance of the tool and useful ways to repurpose the items. This encourages people to gain more knowledge and awareness about e-waste.

2.6 General comment and Conclusion

There are numerous projects and software systems that exist to help solve the challenge of waste management using AI but none developed a fully integrated software where users are educated about e-waste risks and can also upload e-waste items to receive reuse ideas. Also, most of the existing software solutions just focus on classification and disposal rather than offering educational programs and encouraging sustainable reuse of discarded e-waste items. This project will definitely help locals particularly those who live in densely populated neighborhoods like Eastleigh, Nairobi.

CHAPTER THREE: SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the system design and analysis of the e-waste classification, reuse recommendation system and offering educational and awareness resources. It also outlines the research design, how the solution will be implemented and how the important research questions will be addressed. The chapter also discusses the solution functional and non-functional requirements, system architecture, the UML diagrams and the development tools to build the system.

3.2 Research Design

The research design consists of two parts:

- Software development methodology
- Research Methodology

3.2.1 Software Development Methodology

The software development of the project follows the Agile methodology, which highlights the iterative development, continuous testing and regular user feedback. The research uses a mixed-methods approach, where it combines qualitative and quantitative methods. This enables the collection of numerical data on software performance in addition to user feedback through surveys and interviews to evaluate the effectiveness of the software system. Some of the development tools used to build the project are Flask, Tensorflow/Keras, and Flutter.

3.2.2 Research Methodology

The research project adopts a mixed-methods approach to assess the effectiveness of the proposed solution that addresses the e-waste challenge in Nairobi and answers the research questions above.

When it comes to data collection, feedback data will be collected from 10-15 residents of Eastleigh neighborhood to test the solution. They will use the software by uploading some of their e-waste materials and review the reuse ideas recommended for them. After using the software, their feedback data will be collected through surveys and brief interviews.

Furthermore, the success of the software solution will be measured by two criteria. First, the average accuracy rate of the image classification model is expected to be 80% on recognizing e-waste items. Second, nearly 60% of the users who interact with the software must get inspiration from the software creativity and show a positive intention to reuse it to protect their health and environment.

3.3 Functional and Non-functional Requirements

3.3.1. Functional Requirements

- Users upload images of e-waste items.
- The system classifies the item using a trained machine learning model.
- The system suggests reuse ideas for the classified items and shows the practical ways to reuse them.
- Users can also read and explore the offered educational resources.
- Users can access a chatbot that guides them if they need help.

3.3.2. Non-Functional Requirements

- **Accuracy:** the system must classify images with an accuracy of at least 80%.
- **Performance:** the response time for a classification should be under 10 seconds.
- **Usability:** the interface must be mobile-friendly and responsive.
- **Reliability:** the application must be functional at least 99% whenever it is accessed by users.

3.4 System Architecture

The system architecture follows the well-known client-server architecture, where the client-side, web or mobile app interacts with the backend server that handles data storage, security and most importantly enables the functionalities.

3.5 UML Diagrams

3.5.1. ERD diagram

3.5.2. Class diagram

3.5.2. Use Case diagram

3.6 Development Tools

Components	Technology Tools
Front End/Back End	HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Flask
Machine Learning	Tensorflow/Keras, Pytorch
Database	MongoDB, Firebase
Dataset	GitHub
Mobile Development	Flutter

Table 2: Development Tools

CHAPTER FOUR: SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

4.1 Implementation and Coding

4.1.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the features and the functionalities of the proposed software solutions for electronic waste challenge in Nairobi's Eastleigh neighborhood. It will thoroughly explain how the design and functionalities mentioned in chapter three were transformed into a working software application that anyone can use and benefit from. It will also provide screenshots and the codes of key features of the software while explaining how to interact with it.

4.1.2 Description of Implementation Tools and Technology

The implementation of the project followed the agile method, with continuous testing of the following key sections:

- Image classification model (Machine Learning Model using CNNs).
- Identification of e-waste items and suggesting reuse ideas (FastAPI).
- Educational and Awareness through videos, documents and quizzes.
- Curated chatbot (Aitanabot) which only generates information related to e-waste, sustainability and circular economy.
- Both Mobile and Web application support.

For the Web backend, Flask was used to set up all of the routes such as the signup/in, classify, aitanabot, etc. For the mobile application backend, Flask and FastAPI were used for the classify and aitanabot features.

4.1.3. Testing Tools and Technologies

Tool/Technology	Description
Python/Tensorflow/Keras	Training the Machine Learning Model (CNN)
Flask/FastAPI	Building the Web interface and the APIs
Flutter	Developing the Mobile application
Gemini API	Training the chatbot (aitanabot)
MongoDB (Atlas)	Saving the important data, users info, feedback, etc.
Firebase/Local Server	Cloud storage and running the project

Table 3 Testing Tools and Technologies

4.2 Graphical Views

This part will breakdown the core modules and features of the project with screenshots of implementation and codes.

4.2.1. Screenshots with Descriptions

4.2.1.1 The Dashboard - Home Page

The Dashboard is the landing page that appears after the user logs in. It has quick navigation buttons to the main features of the mobile application such as:

- **Classify page:** users upload and analyze their e-waste items.
- **Aitanabot page:** users can ask any questions related to e-waste and circular economy.

- **Education page:** users can benefit from the resources in it such as the videos, documents and quizzes.
- **Settings page:** users can manage their profile page and preferences in this page.

Mobile Application View:

Source Code:

```
lib > screens > dashboard.dart > _DashboardScreenState > build
1  import 'dart:math';
2  import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
3  import 'package:shared_preferences/shared_preferences.dart';
4
5  class DashboardScreen extends StatefulWidget {
6    static const routeName = '/dashboard';
7    const DashboardScreen({Key? key}) : super(key: key);
8
9    @override
10   State<DashboardScreen> createState() => _DashboardScreenState();
11 }
12
13 class _DashboardScreenState extends State<DashboardScreen> with TickerProviderStateMixin {
14   String inspiration = "";
15   late AnimationController _controller;
16   late Animation<Offset> _slideAnimation;
17   late Animation<double> _fadeAnimation;
18
19   final List<String> inspirations = [
20     "🗑️ One person's trash is another person's treasure!",
21     "♻️ Reduce, Reuse, Recycle – and Reinvent.",
22     "💡 E-waste today, innovation tomorrow.",
23     "🌱 Creativity turns waste into wonders.",
24     "🌍 Sustainability starts with you.",
25   ];
26
27   @override
28   void initState() {
29     super.initState();
30     _loadData();
31     _controller = AnimationController(
32       duration: const Duration(milliseconds: 700),
33     ); // AnimationController
34   ); // AnimationController
35   _slideAnimation = Tween<Offset>(
36     begin: const Offset(0, 0.2),
37     end: Offset.zero,
38   ).animate(CurvedAnimation(parent: _controller, curve: Curves.easeOut)); // Tween
39   _fadeAnimation = Tween<double>(begin: 0, end: 1).animate(_controller);
40   _controller.forward();
41 }
42
43 Future<void> _loadData() async {
44   final prefs = await SharedPreferences.getInstance();
45   final random = Random();
46   setState(() {
47     inspiration = inspirations[random.nextInt(inspirations.length)];
48   });
49 }
50
51 @override
52 void dispose() {
53   _controller.dispose();
54   super.dispose();
55 }
56
57 @override
58 Widget build(BuildContext context) {
59   return Scaffold(
60     appBar: AppBar(
61       title: const Text("Aitana Home"),
```

4.2.1.2 The Classify Page

The classify page is where users upload their e-waste items. The system processes the uploaded image using a CNN-based ML model and immediately returns:

- E-waste item names such as Laptop, camera, etc. . It takes 3-10 seconds to identify the item.
- Confidence score (%) which represents how certain the ML model predicted the e-waste item. The average confidence level of the ML model is 86%.
- One fun fact about the identified e-waste item.
- Two practical reuse ideas with links showing how to implement it.

The only limitation about this classification model is that it is only trained to classify on 8 e-waste categories so any other items outside these items may be misclassified.

Mobile Application View:

Source Code:

```
1 import dart:convert;
2 import 'dart:io';
3 import 'dart:typed_data';
4
5 import 'package:flutter/foundation.dart';
6 import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
7 import 'package:http/http.dart' as http;
8 import 'package:image_picker/image_picker.dart';
9 import 'package:url_launcher/url_launcher.dart';
10
11 class ClassifyScreen extends StatefulWidget {
12   const ClassifyScreen({Key? key}) : super(key: key);
13
14   @override
15   State<ClassifyScreen> createState() => _ClassifyScreenState();
16 }
17
18 class _ClassifyScreenState extends State<ClassifyScreen> {
19   File? _image;
20   Uint8List? _webImageBytes;
21   final picker = ImagePicker();
22   bool _loading = false;
23   String? _label;
24   String? _confidence;
25   String? _funFact;
26   List<Map<String, String>> _reuseIdeas = [];
27
28   Future<void> _pickImage() async {
29     final pickedFile = await picker.pickImage(source: ImageSource.gallery);
30
31     if (pickedFile != null) {
32       if (kIsWeb) {
```

```
3   final uri = Uri.parse('https://yasino007-aitana-app-api.hf.space//predict');
4   final request = http.MultipartRequest('POST', uri);
5
6   if (kIsWeb) {
7     request.files.add(
8       http.MultipartFile.fromBytes(
9         'image',
10        _webImageBytes!,
11        filename: 'upload.jpg',
12      ),
13    );
14  } else {
15    request.files.add(
16      await http.MultipartFile.fromPath(
17        'image',
18        _image!.path,
19      ),
20    );
21  }
22
23  try {
24    final streamedResponse = await request.send();
25    final response = await http.Response.fromStream(streamedResponse);
26
27    if (response.statusCode == 200) {
28      final data = jsonDecode(response.body);
29      setState(() {
30        _label = data['label'];
31        _confidence = data['confidence'];
32      });
33    }
34  }
35 }
```

4.2.1.3 The Chatbot (Aitanabot)

Aitanabot is a Google Gemini API-powered chatbot designed and fine-tuned to only answer questions related to e-waste management, circular economy, sustainability and climate change. The average response time of aitanabot is approximately between 5 seconds to 12 seconds. The only limitation of this feature is that it requires internet connection to work.

Mobile Application View:

Source Code:

```
1 import 'dart:convert';
2 import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
3 import 'package:http/http.dart' as http;
4 import 'package:shared_preferences/shared_preferences.dart';
5
6 class AitanaBotScreen extends StatefulWidget {
7   const AitanaBotScreen({Key? key}) : super(key: key);
8
9   @override
10  State<AitanaBotScreen> createState() => _AitanaBotScreenState();
11 }
12
13 class _AitanaBotScreenState extends State<AitanaBotScreen> {
14   final List<_ChatMessage> _messages = [];
15   final TextEditingController _controller = TextEditingController();
16   final ScrollController _scrollCtrl = ScrollController();
17   bool _isSending = false;
18
19   static const String _apiUrl = "https://aitanabot.onrender.com//chat";
20   String? _profileImageBase64;
21
22   @override
23   void initState() {
24     super.initState();
25     _messages.clear();
26     WidgetsBinding.instance.addPostFrameCallback((_) {
27       setState(() {
28         _messages.add(_ChatMessage(
29           text: "Hi there! I'm AITANABOT 🤖. Ask me anything about e-waste, sustainability, or climate change!",
30           isUser: false,
31         ));
32       });
33     });
34   }
35 }
```

```
103 @override
104 Widget build(BuildContext context) {
105   const botAvatar = 'assets/images/aitanabott.png';
106   const userAvatar = 'assets/images/yasino.jpg';
107   const backgroundColor = Colors.white;
108   const userBubble = Color(0xFFD6E6FF); // light blue
109   const botBubble = Color(0xFFF1F5F9); // soft gray
110   const inputFill = Color(0xFFE3F2FD); // soft blue
111
112   return Scaffold(
113     backgroundColor: backgroundColor,
114     appBar: AppBar(
115       title: const Text("🤖 AITANABOT"),
116       backgroundColor: Colors.blue[800],
117       centerTitle: true,
118     ), // AppBar
119     body: SafeArea(
120       child: Column(
121         children: [
122           Expanded(
123             child: ListView.builder(
124               controller: _scrollCtrl,
125               padding: const EdgeInsets.all(16),
126               itemCount: _messages.length,
127               itemBuilder: (context, index) {
128                 final msg = _messages[index];
129                 final avatar = msg.isUser
130                   ? (_profileImageBase64 != null
131                     ? MemoryImage(base64Decode(_profileImageBase64!))
132                     : const AssetImage(userAvatar))
133                 : const AssetImage(botAvatar);
134               },
135             ),
136           ),
137         ],
138       ),
139     ),
140   );
141 }
```

4.2.1.4 The Education Page

The education page is an educational page that contains three different tabs:

- Videos: brief and organized educational videos about circular economy and e-waste and how to handle it and how to be aware of its hazards.
- Documents: articles, journals and pieces of information about the e-waste topic.
- Quiz: multiple choice based questions about e-waste to test the user knowledge and also teach at the same time. It has 50 questions so every time the user starts the quiz, it has limited questions of 10 randomly generated from the 50 questions. At completion of the quiz, the user receives a result like 8/10 if they answered 8 of the questions correctly.

This feature only works with internet connection.

Mobile Application View:

Source Code:

```
1 import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
2 import 'education_videos.dart';
3 import 'education_blogs.dart';
4 import 'education_quiz.dart';
5
6 class EducationScreen extends StatelessWidget {
7   const EducationScreen({super.key});
8
9   @override
10  Widget build(BuildContext context) {
11    return Scaffold(
12      appBar: AppBar(
13        title: const Text('📚 Education'),
14        backgroundColor: Colors.blueAccent,
15        centerTitle: true,
16      ), // AppBar
17      body: Container(
18        decoration: const BoxDecoration(
19          image: DecorationImage(
20            image: AssetImage('assets/images/welcome_background.png'),
21            fit: BoxFit.cover,
22          ), // DecorationImage
23        ), // BoxDecoration
24        child: Center(
25          child: Column(
26            mainAxisAlignment: MainAxisAlignment.center,
27            children: [
28              _buildButton(context, '📺 Videos', const EducationVideosScreen()),
29              const SizedBox(height: 20),
30              _buildButton(context, '📄 Documents', const EducationBlogsScreen()),
31              const SizedBox(height: 20),
32              _buildButton(context, '📝 Quiz', const EducationQuizScreen()),
```

```
32              _buildButton(context, '📝 Quiz', const EducationQuizScreen()),
33            ],
34          ), // Column
35        ), // Center
36      ), // Container
37    ); // Scaffold
38  }
39
40  Widget _buildButton(BuildContext context, String text, Widget page) {
41    return ElevatedButton(
42      onPressed: () {
43        Navigator.push(context, MaterialPageRoute(builder: (_) => page));
44      },
45      style: ElevatedButton.styleFrom(
46        backgroundColor: Colors.blue.shade700,
47        padding: const EdgeInsets.symmetric(horizontal: 50, vertical: 20),
48        shape: RoundedRectangleBorder(
49          borderRadius: BorderRadius.circular(15),
50        ), // RoundedRectangleBorder
51        elevation: 8,
52      ),
53      child: Text(
54        text,
55        style: const TextStyle(fontSize: 20, color: Colors.white),
56      ), // Text
57    ); // ElevatedButton
58  }
59 }
60 }
```

4.2.1.5 The Profile Page

The profile page contains the user's information:

- Name
- Email Address
- Username
- Phone number
- Profile picture

All of this information can be edited and modified except the email address, which cannot be changed for data security reasons.

Mobile Application View:

Source Code:

```
1 import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
2
3 class ProfileScreen extends StatefulWidget {
4   static const routeName = '/profile';
5   const ProfileScreen({super.key});
6
7   @override
8   State<ProfileScreen> createState() => _ProfileScreenState();
9 }
10
11 class _ProfileScreenState extends State<ProfileScreen> {
12   final _nameController = TextEditingController(text: "Mohamed Yasino");
13   final _emailController = TextEditingController(text: "mayasinalu@gmail.com");
14   final _usernameController = TextEditingController(text: "mayasino");
15   final _phoneController = TextEditingController(text: "+250799358985");
16
17   bool _editing = false;
18
19   void _toggleEditing() {
20     setState(() {
21       _editing = !_editing;
22     });
23   }
24
25   void _saveProfile() {
26     // Here you would add logic to save the profile data (e.g., Firebase, SharedPreferences, etc.)
27     ScaffoldMessenger.of(context).showSnackBar(
28       const SnackBar(content: Text('✅ Profile updated successfully')),
29     );
30     setState(() => _editing = false);
31   }
}
```

```
38   return Scaffold(
39     appBar: AppBar(
40       title: const Text("👤 My Profile"),
41       actions: [
42         IconButton(
43           icon: Icon(_editing ? Icons.check : Icons.edit),
44           onPressed: _editing ? _saveProfile : _toggleEditing,
45         ), // IconButton
46       ],
47     ), // AppBar
48     body: Padding(
49       padding: const EdgeInsets.all(20),
50       child: Column(
51         children: [
52           const CircleAvatar(
53             radius: 50,
54             backgroundImage: AssetImage('assets/images/yasino.jpg'),
55           ), // CircleAvatar
56           const SizedBox(height: 20),
57           _buildProfileField("Full Name", _nameController, _editing),
58           const SizedBox(height: 15),
59           _buildProfileField("Email", _emailController, false), |
60           const SizedBox(height: 15),
61           _buildProfileField("Username", _usernameController, _editing),
62           const SizedBox(height: 15),
63           _buildProfileField("Phone", _phoneController, _editing),
64         ],
65       ), // Column
66     ), // Padding
67   ); // Scaffold
```

4.3 Testing

4.3.1 Objective of Testing

The main objective of testing is that Aitana app:

- Identifies the eight e-waste items of the project dataset at a high accuracy rate.
- Suggests practical and useful reuse ideas.
- Helps users learn more about e-waste management.
- Answer questions related to e-waste management and circular economy.

4.3.2 Unit Testing

Component	Test	Status
Image classification	Classify e-waste items	Working
Suggesting Reuse Ideas	recommend practical repurpose ideas	Working
Chatbot	Answer any e-waste related questions	Working
Education	All educational links	Working

Table 4 Unit Testing

4.3.3 Validation Testing

I uploaded a test image of a laptop on the classify page and it correctly classified with 92.9% confidence. I also generated one fun fact and two practical reuse ideas for the laptop. See the image below for reference.

4.3.4 Integration Testing

Integration	Result
E-waste items classification + Firebase/MongoDB	Successful
Chatbot + Gemini API	Working
Sign up + classification + profile update	Seamless

Table 5 Integration Testing

4.3.5 Functional Testing

The functional testing showed that all core features are working seamlessly with no errors and lags. For example, the image classification is classifying the e-waste items in less than 10 seconds. The chatbot is also responding to the inquiries asked in less than 15 seconds.

4.3.6 Acceptance Testing

Acceptance testing was conducted with a group of test users (10-15 residents of Eastleigh), where they interacted with the mobile application and provided feedback through surveys.

Here is some of the results:

How easy was it to upload an image of your e-waste item on the app?

15 responses

Did the app correctly recognize and classify your e-waste item?

15 responses

How helpful were the reuse ideas suggested by the app?

15 responses

Did you find the educational information about e-waste and its dangers clear and useful?

15 responses

4.3.7 Summary

Aitana's implementation phase seamlessly met all testing requirements and all proposed features are fully functional. The tools combined to build the mobile/web application are Flask, FastAPI, Flutter, Python, Firebase, MongoDB and Gemini API. The Hugging face and Render platforms were also used for APIs deployment. All components of testing showed reliability and high accuracy in image classification, recommending reuse ideas and responding to questions through the chatbot.

CHAPTER FIVE: RESULTS AND EVALUATION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter displays the results and the evaluations from the operations of Aitana. The results show how accurate the software system has tackled the e-waste challenges. It allows users to classify their e-waste items, get practical reuse ideas and learn about e-waste management. Each result is backed by screenshot visuals based on actual classification data retrieved from MongoDB. The tools used in this section are Pandas, Pymongo, Matplotlib, MongoDB and Google Colab.

5.2 Problem overview

The purpose of the project was to tackle the e-waste challenges in Kenya, where people irresponsibly dispose of their electronic items. There were no software solutions whether it was websites or mobile applications that were developed to solve this problem. Aitana was created to classify e-waste items using machine learning models, suggest practical repurpose ideas and teach people about how to properly manage e-waste.

These results also relate and address the research objectives set in chapter one, where the goal was that the trained ML model classification was 80%.

5.3 Software results and performance

The following subsections present the software system's results and performance through insights and data visualizations drawn from aitana's MongoDB classification log.

5.3.1 Classification Confidence rate over time

The following Line chart showcases the confidence levels of the classified e-waste items.

As shown in the line chart above, these classifications exceed the model accuracy target of 80%. This shows the model's reliability within the trained dataset.

5.3.2 Number of classification per e-waste items by name

The following bar chart showcases the number of e-waste items classified by name.

As shown above, the bar chart displays the 8 e-waste items the project dataset contains and how many times they are classified. The Keyboard and Smartwatch are the e-waste items that are frequently classified (5 classifications each).

5.3.3 User engagement activity

The following line chart contains the number of classifications made by day.

The visualization displays that the classification increases over time as it went from making less than four classifications to making more than 20 classifications per day. This growing user engagement could be a powerful positive sign for scale-up, where daily classifications can be tracked as a measure of community participation and awareness.

5.4 Result interpretation

- High confidence rate: The software system’s classification was about 90% most of the time indicating that model’s great accuracy.
- E-waste items: The number of e-waste items classified, showing their threats in the project area.

- Continuous classifications: The visualizations show that the software system usage increases fast over time.

These above findings closely align with the project objectives. The high accuracy rate shows technical success, while the growth in e-waste items classifications points to positive user adoption.

5.5 Limitations

- Although the confidence rate is high, some e-waste items may still be misclassified due to limited training data.
- The e-waste items are limited to only 8 items and it may not represent all of the e-waste items disposed improperly in the environment.
- Some of the suggested practical reuse ideas may need some sort of skill to be implemented.
- Internet dependency.

5.6 Evaluations

The Aitana system has exhibited that with tools like internet access and smartphone, users can simply identify their e-waste items and get immediate practical repurpose suggestions. Also, all the key features of Aitana such as the image classification model, the chatbot, education and awareness content are functioning seamlessly and meet the research objectives.

These evaluations recommend that Aitana Application can serve as a technical tool and an educational platform. If scaled beyond Kenya, it could reduce e-waste challenges, minimize health risks from improper e-waste disposal, protect the environment and most importantly, raise awareness about adopting sustainable e-waste management practices.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

The Aitana software system was developed to address the growing challenge of electronic waste in Kenya, by using Artificial Intelligence tools to classify e-waste items and then recommend reuse ideas. The project effectively combined key components of image classification, educational awareness, and a customized chatbot into interactive user-friendly mobile and web applications. Software system tests conducted revealed a high model accuracy rate for the e-waste items (over 90%). The testing also directly showed how we can repurpose our e-waste materials into useful items by receiving positive feedback from users.

These outcomes are in line with previous research that highlighted the role of Machine Learning in waste management (Dsouza, 2024). Aitana also aligns the 2030 agenda for Sustainable Development Goals section of accelerating circular economy solutions (Khajuria et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the Aitana system helps teach people about e-waste management and the circular economy. It does this by providing useful resources such as videos, documents and quizzes that empower users to be aware of e-waste dangers to the environment.

6.2 Limitations of the study

Despite Aitana's software system success, there are several limitations such as:

- The project dataset is small and it only includes 8 types of e-waste, which limits Aitana's scope and generalization.
- Some of the recommended reuse ideas are not personalized so it may not be beneficial to the users. The reuse ideas are also limited.

- Internet access can be a challenge as Aitana only works with the internet.

6.3 Recommendations

To enhance and better Aitana's impact and user experience, the following actions are highly recommended:

- Expand the e-waste dataset: add more diverse e-waste materials and collect different types of e-waste images to increase generalization.
- More repurposing ideas: include more practical reuse ideas that are useful and easy to implement.
- Offline Version: add offline features of Aitana so users with no internet access or limited internet connections can still benefit from it.
- Partnerships: collaborating with schools, NGOs, local organizations and the government agencies to deploy Aitana and support the mission and vision behind it.

6.4 Further studies

Future studies and development may focus on the following:

- Introducing object detection like YOLOv8 to locate and detect e-waste items more efficiently.
- Adding language support and audio support for users with low literacy or visual impairments.
- Introducing gamified learning feature that has quizzes, badges, and loyalty points to make learning more engaging and fun for users.
- Developing a simple offline version of Aitana to reach and support users with poor internet access.

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